

The Solar System Terraforming Project

Period of Time: 27th-34th century

Company: **NAR** (Ndoni Advanced Robotics)

Number of humanoid robots involved in the process of creating habitats: 500B+

Number of (potentially) hosted citizens: 10-50T+

Purpose: After terraforming the entire Solar System, use advanced robotics and machinery to build a habitat for (potentially) hosting 10-50T+ citizens.

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